

Generate simulated data & apply Instrumental Variable (IV) method. Takes approximately 15 seconds.

```
library("ivreg")
```

```
n <- 100 # Sample size.  
ntrial <- 1000 # Number of trials.  
ols = olsadj = iv = numeric(ntrial) # Space for storing 4 estimates.  
sigma <- 3 # Treatment & outcome noise sigma.
```

```
for(trial in 1:ntrial){  
  set.seed(trial)  
  z <- rnorm(n,0,1) # The instrument.  
  u <- rnorm(n,0,1) # Confounder, uncorrelated with instrument.  
  x <- 2*z + 3*u + rnorm(n, 0, sigma) # Model for treatment.  
  y <- 1*x + 2*u + rnorm(n, 0, sigma) # Model for outcome; treatment effect = 1  
  
  ols[trial] <- lm(y ~ x)$coef[2]  
  olsadj[trial] <- lm(y ~ x + u)$coef[2]  
  iv[trial] <- ivreg(y ~ x | z)$coefficients[2]  
}
```

```
boxplot(ols, olsadj, iv, range = 0, xlab="",  
        ylab="ATE Confidence Interval", axes=F)  
axis(1, labels=c("OLS", "OLS+adj", "IV"), at=c(1:3))  
axis(2, labels=T)  
abline(h=1.0, lt=2)
```

```
n <- 10^8 # One large sample for generating correlation matrix.  
set.seed(1)  
z <- rnorm(n,0,1)  
u <- rnorm(n,0,1)  
x <- 2*z + 3*u + rnorm(n, 0, sigma)  
y <- 1*x + 2*u + rnorm(n, 0, sigma)  
round(cor(cbind(x,y,u,z)),2)
```